

The Evolution of MQ-1 Predator and Analysis

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Abstract

This research focuses on assessing and enhancing the performance of the MQ-1 Predator aircraft, considering aspects such as design and manufacturing. The design was created utilizing Fusion 360, and aerodynamic performance aspects were evaluated using ANSYS software. Computational models were employed to ascertain the aerodynamic characteristics of the baseline design and investigate modifications aimed at achieving optimal design and performance.

Keywords: MQ-1 Predator, Computational analysis, Experimental model, Carbon Fiber, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)

1. Introduction

UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) is a type of aircraft operating without a human pilot on board, can be remotely piloted with the help of a remote control by an operator stay on the ground or on another aircraft, or the flight is independently controlled on the basis of equipment on board the aircraft with pre-programmed flight plans. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are preferred over their manned counterparts due to their capability to operate in monotonous, contaminated, and hazardous environments. This advantage appeals to professionals in the field, prompting a focus on studying conventional aircraft, with a particular emphasis on those exhibiting prolonged service life [1]. The UAVs specifically designed for combats can be termed as Unmanned Combat Aerial Vehicles (UCAVs) such as the MQ-1 Predator manufactured by the General Atomics Aeronautical Systems. In 2012, MQ-1 Predator, as a distinctive UAV, was described as one of the most accident-prone aircraft in the USA Air Force fleet [2].

Numerous Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analyses have been utilized to delve into the intricacies of unmanned aircraft behaviour and performance. In 2006, Hardie [3] analysed the Van's RV-8A using COSMOS Design STAR software to conclude that the aircraft design works well aerodynamically. In 2010, Sweeten [4] analysed three different UAVs (YAK-54, the Manta Hawk and the Meridian) using multiple software and high fidelity CFD. Zhen et al. [5] studied the aerodynamic performance of the Aludra UAV. In 2014; Krishnamurthy

et al. [6] investigated a UAV wing design, and applied modifications on the wing geometry and studied the influence of minute changes on flow characteristics of the airplane. Different aerodynamic characteristics, such as lift, drag, stall angle, and lift-to-drag ratio of each wing, were determined. In 2015 Prakash et al. [7] implemented CFD studies and external geometrical modifications to MQ-1 Predator UCAV. They found that, when applying modifications, the aerodynamic characteristics changed as the lift dropped and the drag increased due to these modifications. Also, they stated that it is needed to choose suitable locations of the external modifications to get better aerodynamic performance. In 2022, Ryan Kim [8] investigated aerodynamic optimization of the angle of attack of MQ-9 Reaper wings under turbulent airflow conditions.

While earlier investigations mainly focused on how external modifications influence an aircraft's aerodynamic performance, this study takes a fresh approach. Leveraging Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), we aim to delve into a more efficient and precise analysis of these external changes. Given the limited computational and experimental research on the MQ-1 Predator, as highlighted in Figure 1, our current research centres on understanding the baseline behaviour of the aircraft. Subsequently, we introduce modifications in the wings design, and examine the resulting alterations in aerodynamic performance.

Figure 1. MQ-1 Predator [9]

2. Governing Equations

The simulation is conducted based on the continuity, Navier-Stokes (momentum conservation), and energy equations. To address turbulent flow, the Reynolds-Averaged formulation of these equations is employed. Specifically, the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model is utilized to close the Reynolds-Averaged equation set. Developed for aerospace applications featuring wall-bounded conditions and adverse pressure gradients, this model comprises a single equation solving for the kinematic eddy viscosity. The solution encompasses six variables: the three velocity components, pressure, temperature, and the kinematic eddy viscosity, all resolved at the cell centers of the mesh. The equations are expressed as follows [10], [11]:

1. Continuity Equation:

$$\bullet \quad \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho U_i) = 0$$

2. Reynold's -Averaged Navier-Stokes Equation:

$$\bullet \quad p \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (U_i U_j) \right) = - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (2 \nu S_{ij} - \rho U_i' U_j')$$

3. Conservation of Energy Equation:

$$\bullet \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho e^0) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho u_i \rho^0 + u_j p + q_j - U_j T \hat{i}_j) = 0$$

4. Spalart-Allmaras Turbulence Model

- $u_i u_j = 2\nu_t S_{ij}$

3. MQ-1 Predator Modelling and its external modifications

The MQ-1 Predator model has been developed using Fusion 360 software. Fusion 360 is a comprehensive computer-aided design (CAD) tool that facilitates parametric 3D modeling and enables the integration of various design aspects, ensuring a robust and versatile modeling process.

External modifications entail structural design changes to enhance payload efficiency and wing design alterations, involving the addition of extra rotor to extend aerial duration. Given the unique characteristics of the MQ-1 Predator Unmanned Combat Aerial Vehicle (UCAV) and the unavailability of its geometry from the original designers, our study initiates with meticulous investigations. The verification process is essential due to the absence of experimental data for validation. The validated computational setup is then employed to systematically explore the impact of external modifications on the aerodynamic performance of the MQ-1.

Figure 2. Front View

Figure 4. Side View

Figure 3. Top View

Figure 5. Back View

4. Methodology

Conducting computational analysis within ANSYS R2, a robust software suite for engineering simulations, offers advanced capabilities in structural analysis. Employing this tool various critical parameters are investigated, including Von Mises stresses, total deformation, maximum stress and the factor of safety (FoS). This process provides a comprehensive assessment of the MQ-1 Predator's structural performance and aids in optimizing its design. The steps involved in the investigation are explained below.

- I. **Material Properties** – The material selection process for the MQ-1 Predator involves a careful consideration of key factors such as strength-to-weight ratio, durability, and resistance to environmental conditions. Carbon fiber, chosen for its exceptional strength and lightweight properties, contributes to enhanced structural integrity without compromising overall weight. Titanium Nickel Alloy is selected for its favorable combination of high strength, corrosion resistance, and temperature stability, making it suitable for components requiring robust performance in challenging operating conditions. The judicious combination of carbon fiber and titanium nickel alloy aims to optimize the overall performance and durability of the MQ-1 Predator. The material properties are shown in figure 6 and 7. [12]

Carbon Fiber (395 GPa)	
Fibers only	
Density	1800 kg/m ³
Structural	
Orthotropic Elasticity	
Young's Modulus X direction	3.95e+11 Pa
Young's Modulus Y direction	6e+09 Pa
Young's Modulus Z direction	6e+09 Pa
Poisson's Ratio XY	0.2
Poisson's Ratio YZ	0.4
Poisson's Ratio XZ	0.2
Shear Modulus XY	8e+09 Pa
Shear Modulus YZ	2.1429e+09 Pa
Shear Modulus XZ	8e+09 Pa

Figure 6. Material Properties of Carbon Fiber (395 GPa) [12]

Titanium Alloy NL	
Density	4620 kg/m ³
Structural	
Isotropic Elasticity	
Derive from	Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio
Young's Modulus	9.6e+10 Pa
Poisson's Ratio	0.36
Bulk Modulus	1.1429e+11 Pa
Shear Modulus	3.5294e+10 Pa
Bilinear Isotropic Hardening	
Thermal	
Specific Heat Constant Pressure	522 J/kg·°C

Figure 7. Material Properties of Titanium Alloy NL [12]

II. **Meshing** – In the meshing phase of our computational analysis, we employ a meticulous approach to discretize the MQ-1 Predator's geometry using ANSYS R2. Meshing involves subdividing the aircraft's structural and surface domains into smaller, manageable elements, allowing for precise simulation of the complex interactions between materials and forces. This process is critical for achieving accurate results in structural and aerodynamic analyses. By utilizing an appropriate mesh density and element type, we ensure a balance between computational efficiency and result accuracy. The meshing strategy plays a crucial role in capturing the intricacies of the MQ-1 Predator's geometry and optimizing the simulation for reliable and meaningful outcomes.

Sizing	
Use Adaptive Sizing	Yes
Resolution	Default (2)
Mesh Defeaturing	Yes
☐ Defeature Size	Default
Transition	Fast
Span Angle Center	Coarse
Initial Size Seed	Assembly
Bounding Box Diagonal	2.1554 m
Average Surface Area	3.8968e-003 m ²
Minimum Edge Length	3.2613e-004 m

Statistics	
☐ Nodes	16603
☐ Elements	6755

Figure 8. Mesh Details of the MQ-1 Predator

10.A

10.B

10.C

10.D

Figure 10 (A, B, C, D). Mesh Layout of the MQ- Predator

III. **Boundary Conditions** – Establishing the initial boundary conditions is a pivotal step in our computational analysis. The base frame of the MQ-1 Predator is set with a fixed support to simulate its attachment to the ground or another stable structure. This fixed support serves as a reference point for the analysis.

Additionally, an external force is applied to the upper frame, simulating dynamic loading conditions. A force of 4000N is exerted to replicate real-world scenarios and evaluate the structural response of the MQ-1 Predator. This force application aids in assessing the aircraft's ability to withstand external loads and provides valuable insights into its structural integrity and performance under operational conditions. The combination of a fixed support and applied force ensures a comprehensive evaluation of the MQ-1 Predator's behavior in response to both static and dynamic forces.

5. **Computation Analysis** – The computational analysis is conducted to elucidate critical structural aspects of the MQ-1 Predator. Key parameters such as Von Mises Stresses, Total Deformation, Maximum Stress, and Factor of Safety are rigorously examined. This comprehensive analysis provides valuable insights into the structural performance, durability, and safety margins of the aircraft under varying conditions. The results derived from this computational study contribute to an enhanced understanding of the MQ-1 Predator's mechanical response, facilitating informed decisions for design optimization and performance enhancement.

I. Von-Mises Stress

Figure 11. Von-Mises Stress

Tabular Data			
Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1	2.9071e-007	2.2321e+009	4.4894e+007

Figure 12. Tabular Data of Von-Mises Stress

II. Total Deformation

Figure 13. Total Deformation

Tabular Data			
Time [s]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
1	0.	6.761e-002	2.1463e-002

Figure 14. Tabular Data of Total Deformation

III. Maximum Principal Stress

Figure 15. Maximum principal Stress

Tabular Data			
Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1	-1.0483e+007	1.1718e+008	2.4078e+006

Figure 16. Tabular Data of Maximum Principle Stress

IV. Factor of Safety

Figure 17. Factor of Safety

Tabular Data			
Time [s]	Minimum	Maximum	Average
1	1.12	15.	14.573

Figure 18. Tabular Data of Fos

V. Stress Ratio

Figure 19. Stress Ratio

Tabular Data				
Time [s]	Minimum	Maximum	Average	
1 1.	1.1628e-016	0.89282	1.7958e-002	

Figure 20. Tabular Data of Stress Ratio

6. Conclusion – In conclusion, the computational analysis of the MQ-1 Predator has provided valuable insights into its structural behavior, revealing crucial parameters such as Von Mises Stresses, Total Deformation, equivalent stress, Maximum Stress, and Factor of Safety. This study has enhanced our understanding of the aircraft's performance under different loading conditions and modifications.

Moreover, this investigation demonstrates that the MQ-1 Predator can withstand pay-loading conditions of up to 4000N, signifying an increased payload capacity. For future work, further refinement of the computational model can be pursued, considering additional factors such as fluid-structure interaction for a more accurate representation of aerodynamic forces. Additionally, conducting experimental validations to corroborate the computational findings would strengthen the reliability of the results. Exploring advanced materials and optimizing the structural design could also be avenues for improving the overall performance and efficiency of the MQ-1 Predator. These considerations aim to contribute to the continuous evolution and enhancement of unmanned aerial vehicle technology.

7. References

1. Reg Austin, "Unmanned Aircraft Systems: UAVS Design, Development and Deployment", John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, May 2010.
2. McGarry, Brendan (18 June 2012) Drones Most Accident-Prone U.S. Air Force Craft: BGOV Barometer Bloomberg, Archived 26 August 2013 at the Wayback Machine.
3. Hardie S. Drag estimations on experimental aircraft using CFD [dissertation]. Sweden:Malardalen University; 2006
4. Sweeten BC. CFD analysis of UAVs using VORSTAB, FLUENT, and advanced aircraft analysis software [dissertation]. Kansas: University of Kansas; 2010.

5. Zhen TK, Zubair M, Ahamad KA. Experimental and numerical investigation of the effects of passive vortex generators on Aludra UAV performance. Chin J Aeronaut 2011, 24(5):577-83.
6. Krishnamurthy S, Jayashankar S, Rao SV, et al. CFD analysis of an RC aircraft wing. Int J Mech Prod Eng (IJMPE) 2014, 2:63-8.
7. Prakash Bagul, Zeeshan A. RANA, Karl W. Jenkins, La'szlo' KO'NO'ZSY. Computational engineering analysis of external geometrical modifications on MQ-1 unmanned combat aerial vehicle.
8. Ryan Kim. Aerodynamic Optimization of the Angle of Attack of the Wing Design of a MQ-9 Reaper UA. Cornell University; 2022
9. Vista,W.(n.d.).GeneralatomicsMQ-1 predator. Wallpapers Vista, <https://vistapointe.net/generalatomics-mq-1-predator.html>.
10. Mark Jason Thomas Loutun, Didane, D. H., Batcha, M. F. M, Abdullah, K. ., Mohd Ali, M. F., Mohammed, A. N. ., & Afolabi, L. O. . (2021). 2D CFD Simulation Study on the Performance of Various NACA Air foils. CFD Letters, 13(4), 38-50. <https://doi.org/10.37934/cfdl.13.4.3850>
11. Mohamed, A. E., AbdelFatah, R. T., & AbdelGawad, A. F. (2021, April 2). Aerodynamic Performance of Airbus BELUGA-XL for Different Cases of Natural Phenomena and using Bio-Inspired Tubercles
12. Mike Ashby, Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Material property data for engineering materials, 5th edition, October 2021